

A TWO PHASES COUPLING FREE AND POROUS FLOW METHOD AT MULTI-SCALES OF LCM PROCESS

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Numerical Simulation of Liquid Composite Molding Processes at Multi-Scales

Cahn-Hilliard-Navier-Stokes-Darcy (CHNSD) two-phase flow model

Governing equations

Free domain

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_F}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u}_F \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u}_F \right) = \nabla \cdot [-p_F \mathbf{I} + \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u}_F + (\nabla \mathbf{u}_F)^T)] + \rho \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{F}$$

$$\rho \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u}_F) = 0$$

Front tracking - Cahn-Hilliard

$$\begin{cases} \psi = -\nabla \cdot (e^2 \nabla \phi) + \phi(\phi^2 - 1) \\ \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_F \cdot \nabla \phi = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\gamma \beta}{e^2} \nabla \psi \right) \end{cases} \quad (\text{air}) -1 < \psi < 1 \quad (\text{resin})$$

Porous media

$$\mathbf{u}_{pf} = -\frac{K_p k_r}{\mu_p} (\nabla p_{pf} - \rho_f \mathbf{g}) \quad \begin{bmatrix} K_{xx} & K_{xy} \\ K_{yx} & K_{yy} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\varepsilon \frac{\partial (\rho_f S_f)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_f \mathbf{u}_{pf}) = \rho_f q_f, \quad f = r \text{ for resin, } a \text{ for air}$$

Coupling condition on the interface of porous region and free flow region

Continuity of normal flux $\mathbf{u}_F \cdot \mathbf{n}_{pf} = \mathbf{u}_{pf} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{pf}$

Continuity of normal stress $\mathbf{n}_{pf} \cdot [(-p_F \mathbf{I} + \boldsymbol{\tau}) \mathbf{n}_{pf}] = -\left(\frac{1+\phi}{2} P_{pr} + \frac{1-\phi}{2} P_{pa} \right) = -\left(P_{pr} + \frac{1+\phi}{2} P_{pc} \right)$

BJS boundary condition $\mathbf{t}_{pFi} \cdot [(-p_F \mathbf{I} + \boldsymbol{\tau}) \mathbf{n}_{pf}] = -\mathbf{t}_{pFi} \cdot \frac{\mu \eta(S_r)}{\sqrt{K_p k_r(S_r)}} \mathbf{u}_F$

Tangential stress jump condition

Perspectives

Generation of 3D braided reinforcement

3D braided or woven unit cell model

Macro-scale (Part level)

